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DO HIGHER EDUCATION ENTRANCE EXAMS PREDICT SUCCESS IN ENGINEERING STUDY?

R Prince

University of Cape Town
Cape Town, South Africa
0000-0002-8640-799X

Z Simpson¹

University of Johannesburg
Johannesburg, South Africa
0000-0002-1263-3812

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ABSTRACT

In South Africa, as elsewhere in the world, graduation rates in engineering study are notoriously low. A 2017 report by the American Society for Engineering Education, for example, shows that fewer than 40% of students who enter into an engineering qualification in the United States graduate in the minimum time of four years. This paper investigates the predictive value of the national higher education (HE) entrance exam in South Africa, the National Benchmark Tests (NBTs), for success in engineering study in one HE institution in South Africa. The NBTs attempt to redress the problem of poor throughput and graduation rates by providing institutions with more information about the preparedness of school-leavers prior to entry into HE. In South Africa, the NBTs include three assessments, one each in academic literacy, quantitative literacy and mathematics. The performance of students in these three assessments was captured and correlated with student success in engineering study (measured as either having graduated, continuing study or having dropped out). Across all three assessments, it was found that there is a correlation between performance on the NBTs and success in engineering study, and that performance on the NBTs offers the potential for a rich and nuanced understanding of student success in engineering.

¹ *Corresponding Author*

Z Simpson

zsimpson@uj.ac.za

1 INTRODUCTION

Higher education in South Africa – including engineering education – is characterised by low throughput rates and high dropout rates. This problem is not unique to South Africa: in the United States, the American Society for Engineering Education [1] shows that fewer than 40% of students who enter into an engineering qualification graduate in the minimum time of four years. Nonetheless, in South Africa, these challenges are exacerbated by the particular historical inequities that have shaped the country's history. In particular, the legacy of apartheid has meant that higher education participation and success continue to be skewed along racial lines.

In the first instance, participation rates in higher education in South Africa are low (at only 19% of school-leavers in 2015, the most recent statistics available) [2, p. 5], particularly amongst black school-leavers (only 16% in 2015) [2, p. 5]. Making matters worse, in addition to these low participation rates, graduation rates are low and dropout rates high. In four-year degree programmes, such as those offered in engineering, only 47.9% of the 2015 entering cohort graduated in minimum time, while 13.5% dropped out [3, p. 29]. Again, these graduation rates are skewed along racial lines.

One of the strategies to overcome this situation was the effort of Higher Education South Africa (HESA) to develop the National Benchmark Tests Project (NBTP). This project saw the development of a suite of assessments aimed at establishing the preparedness of South African school-leavers for the demands of higher education. Since their introduction, several higher education institutions in the country now use the National Benchmark Tests (NBTs) for a variety of reasons, including selection, placement and curriculum reform.

This paper investigates whether or not the NBTs are indeed suitable predictors of success – in engineering study, specifically. It does this by analysing the performance of a particular cohort of students over six years in an engineering faculty in a university in South Africa. First, however, it discusses the relevant literature pertaining to school-leaving and university entrance testing.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

In South Africa, specifically, the contribution that the National Senior Certificate (NSC – the statutory national school-leaving examinations) and the National Benchmark Tests (NBT) could play in terms of admission and placement has been investigated by a number of authors [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10]. These authors have examined their effectiveness at predicting success and generated varying conclusions, as is summarised in the paragraphs that follow.

Some studies have found that particular school and entrance exam scores have more predictive power in specific contexts than others. Allers et al. [4], for example, compared the NSC results and NBT results of second-year Physiology students in 2011 and concluded that achievement of high marks in the NSC subjects, English

and Life Sciences and the NBT Quantitative Literacy test were predictors of success in Physiology. The NBT, according to these authors, “could have some value in predicting the success of candidates in their second year of study” [4, p. 83]. Jacobs et al. [5] also found that both the NSC and the NBT Mathematics tests have predictive value. They investigated the predictive power of the NSC Mathematics results and the NBT for success in first year university science courses and recommended a strategy for post-admission placement of students that includes the use of NBT scores. Du Plessis and Gerber [7] examined the recommendations of the NBT Project that to be successful in university-level Mathematics, students’ NBT scores should place them in the Proficient category. Their data showed that students whose scores placed them in the Basic category were not able to succeed in their university Mathematics modules. Their conclusion was that higher NBT scores were necessary for success in university courses such as Actuarial Science and Mathematics, but they were not necessary in courses such as biological, earth, and agricultural sciences. In the European context, Häkkinen [11] compared the predictive value of school results and university entrance exams in three fields (social science, engineering and education) and finds that, while in education, school results are a better predictor of success, the opposite is true in social science and, especially, in engineering. Similarly, in Flanders, positioning tests were found to be able to discriminate between students who achieved high, middle and low success in engineering and science degrees, specifically [12].

Other studies have found that admissions test scores overall were a predictor of success in specific university courses and that combining them with school scores improved predictive ability. For example, in examining the predictive ability of the NBT and the NSC at two South African universities for success in an identical first-year Economics test in order to determine whether NBT scores should be used as a determining factor in university admissions, Rankin et al. [6] concluded that the NSC marks on their own were better predictors of success in the Economics test than the NBT scores on their own, but that combining the scores improved the tests’ predictive ability: “a combination of NSC Mathematics marks and the full set of NBT scores improves the predictive power [of the NSC] significantly” [6, p. 579]. Prince et al. [10], having studied the performance of Engineering students over four years, recommend that, “due to the clear contribution which the NBT aggregate score makes in explaining subsequent performance, the NBT aggregate score could be used in addition to the NSC aggregate score for selection and placement”.

Still further studies have focussed on the ability of entrance exams to assist in the development of teaching and learning interventions. For example, Case et al. [8] argue that in general, NBT results show that most students are under-prepared for university study and that therefore, placement in extended curriculum programmes would be appropriate, while Cliff [9] argues for the use of the NBT AL test scores to determine the level of preparedness of first-time entering university students and to assist in developing teaching and learning interventions that could help improve students’ performance.

Generally, the literature suggests that there is a relationship between university entrance examinations and subsequent higher education performance, whether in the form of grade point average [13] or successful completion [14]. The current study builds on this foregoing research and focusses on a cohort from the Engineering and the Built Environment Faculty at a South African University to investigate the ability of the NBTs in explaining performance in Engineering studies at the end of four and six years.

3 METHODOLOGY

The NBTs are a suite of three assessments, focusing on academic literacy, quantitative literacy and mathematics. In some disciplines, only the first two tests are written but in disciplines such as engineering, all three assessments are completed. As such, this paper examines performance on all three assessments and compares this with performance in a four-year engineering degree programme undertaken at a university in South Africa. Performance on the NBTs is captured as a score out of 100.

Performance in engineering degree study is captured in terms of overall outcome of study after both four years (the minimum duration of the programme) and six years (two years longer than the expected duration of the programme). Overall outcome is captured as either QUAL (meaning that the student has graduated), CONT (meaning the student is still continuing their studies), or RENN (meaning the student has either dropped out or failed). Two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the relationship between overall outcome (after both four and six years) and performance on each of the three NBT assessments.

This analysis is undertaken on one cohort of students, over a period of six years. This cohort consists of 856 first-time entering students in an engineering faculty at a higher education institution in South Africa. Of these students, only 268 (31.3%) graduated in minimum time (four years), while 541 (63.2%) graduated after six years. After four years, 226 (26.4%) had dropped out or failed, which decreased to 223 (26.1%) after six years, as students who drop out may return after placing their studies in abeyance (albeit within limits). As a result, after four years, 362 (42.3%) of the students were continuing with their studies, of which 92 (10.7%) were still continuing after six years.

What is noteworthy about these student outcomes is that less than one-third of students graduated in the expected, or minimum, time – and at least a quarter never graduated. Hence, this study seeks to determine whether the NBT assessments offer any predictive value with regard to these outcomes.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows the mean scores obtained in the NBT Academic Literacy (AL) assessment for the cohort of first-time entering students, grouped according to their overall outcome after four years. The figure also shows the medians and inter-quartile ranges for each group. As can be seen in the figure, those students who

performed better – on average – on the NBT AL assessment were more likely to graduate in minimum time (QUAL). Similarly, those continuing their studies outperformed those who had dropped out or failed (RENN). The same pattern can be seen in Fig. 2, which shows the mean scores (and median and inter-quartile ranges) for each group after six years. As is to be expected, there is little change in the RENN group, as almost all the drop out in the programme occurs within the first four years, and there is little drop out thereafter. As is also to be expected, the gap between the QUAL and CONT groups narrows after six years, as a number of those in the CONT group in Fig. 1 subsequently joined the QUAL group in Fig. 2. In the case of the NBT AL assessment, there are statistically significant differences between all groups, after both periods of time, except between the QUAL and CONT groups after six years ($p = 0.056$). This is different, as will be shown, from the other assessments and suggests that, while AL may be a good identifier of those students who may fail or drop out of engineering study, and those who will graduate in the minimum time, it offers less explanatory potential regarding those students who remain in the system beyond four years, suggesting that other factors are more likely at play amongst such students.

Fig. 1. NBT AL scores, grouped by outcome, after four years; $F(2,797)=42.47$, $p<0.001$

Fig. 2. NBT AL scores, grouped by outcome, after six years; $F(2,797)=27.3$, $p<0.001$

A similar pattern was seen with regard to the NBT Quantitative Literacy (QL) assessment. This can be seen in Fig. 3 (which shows the performance of the cohort of students, grouped according to overall outcome after four years) and in Fig. 4 (which shows this performance after six years). Again, the differences between all three groups were found to be statistically significant for the data after four years and six years ($p < 0.05$), with the only exception being the difference between the CONT and RENN groups after six years ($p = 0.1$). This differs from the finding for the NBT AL assessment, and suggests that performance on the NBT QL assessment is a more reliable predictor of long-term retention, suggesting that students with lower NBT QL scores are unlikely to be successful in engineering study, even after an extended period of six years (which, nominally, is the maximum time allowed to complete an engineering degree, though this is not always strictly enforced).

Fig. 3. NBT QL scores, grouped by outcome, after four years; $F(2,797)=45.25$, $p<0.001$

Fig. 4. NBT QL scores, grouped by outcome, after six years; $F(2,797)=29.37$, $p<0.001$

Finally, with regard to the NBT Maths assessment, the same patterns emerge. After four years, those students who graduated in the minimum expected time outperformed both other groups, and those continuing their studies showed better

results in the NBT Maths assessment than those who had dropped out or failed. The same applies after six years, albeit that the gap between the QUAL and CONT groups narrows. All of these differences were found to be statistically significant except, again, between the CONT and RENN groups after six years. Again, this suggests that students with low NBT Maths scores are unlikely to successfully complete engineering study, even after six years.

Fig. 5. NBT Maths scores, grouped by outcome, after four years; $F(2,752)=50.2$, $p<0.001$

Fig. 6. NBT Maths scores, grouped by outcome, after six years; $F(2,752)=30.15$, $p<0.001$

5 CONCLUSIONS

Performance on the NBTs appears to offer the potential for rich and nuanced understanding of student success in engineering. As has been shown, all three NBT assessments offer some predictive value for determining success in engineering study – particularly within four years. This paper has focused on drop out, continuation and completion only, and further research should also focus on student experiences as well as performance, in the form of student grades.

Nonetheless, the paper has shown that, in the case of all three NBT assessments, it is possible to discern that performance on these assessments might be useful for predicting ultimate success, and success in minimum time specifically. This is because, in the case of all three assessments, there is a statistically significant difference between the performance of those students who graduate in the minimum expected time of four years, and those who do not. However, after six years, this difference is lessened, such that, in the case of the NBT Academic Literacy assessment, at least, the difference ceases to be statistically significant. This suggests that there is a group of students who, with additional support and time, are able to 'catch up' to those students who perform better in the NBT assessments. If institutions of higher learning can gather this information with a view to identifying such students and offering the necessary additional support, these students may be assisted to complete their studies more quickly, thus overcoming, perhaps only in part, one of the major challenges facing higher education in South Africa and elsewhere, namely, poor throughput.

An issue that remains to be discussed is that of student dropout and failure. Although this paper demonstrates that students who perform poorly on the various NBT assessments are more likely to drop out or fail, the solution cannot be to simply exclude such students from higher education, given that higher education participation rates are already low. Instead, greater research needs to be conducted to understand where and how students who perform poorly on the NBT assessments – as a measure of preparedness for higher education – can be additionally supported to nonetheless achieve success at university. Indeed, we would argue that this is the singular challenge facing universities in South Africa, and elsewhere. Higher education admissions tests may offer some support in this regard – though a need for additional investigation remains.

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